

**Circular
Cities & Regions
Initiative**

Knowledge Hub

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Network Coordination Guidelines-1 / D1.2

WP 1, T 1.3

Authors: Mireia Ferri, Alba Matamoros (KVC)

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v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
0.1	29/02/2024	Kveloce	Mireia Ferri
0.2	06/03/2024	Kveloce	Alba Matamoros
0.3	20/03/2024	EURADA	Jerome Friedrichs
0.4	20/03/2024	Kveloce	Mireia Ferri
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1.2	07/03/2025	ICONS	Marcello Bardellini
1.3	17/03/2025	EURADA	Jose Carpintero Molina
2	20/03/2025	KVC	Mireia Ferri Sanz

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Executive summary

The Deliverable 1.2 provides **practical guidelines that describe in detail the coordination mechanisms and tools** to be used to ensure effective coordination between CCRI Knowledge Hub, the DG Research and Innovation, the CCRI-Coordination and Support Office (CSO), other CCRI supporters, and other partnering organisations and interested stakeholders. In brief, this document contains a description of the 3-level circular model of Collaboration, Coordination and Cooperation and their tools. These **3-levels** are:

- **1st level:** With the CCRI (EC, RTD), the CCRI-CSO, and other CCRI supporters (CCRI-CSA project, EIB and Circle Economy).
- **2nd level:** with the potential new partnering organisations.
- **3rd level:** with the potential new CCRI pilots, fellows, projects, partnering organisations members, and other interested stakeholders.

Key findings and lessons learnt:

- The focus of the CCRI Knowledge Hub is to enlarge the CCRI network with new members and complement the activities that already are being implemented by CCRI, supporters and partnering organisations.
- From the four main domains addressed in the CCRI Knowledge Hub, more efforts will be dedicated to technology and impact evaluation.
- Special focus will be made to engage new members coming from academia and business, as requested by the CCRI.
- All communication with existing CCRI members (projects, pilots and fellows) should be undertaken by the CCRI-CSO, as they have already been in contact with these members.

Actions implemented:

- Close communication with the **1st level** via email, periodic meetings, and shared excel file and SharePoint space is crucial for align the work and not duplicate efforts and overwhelm the audience.
- A collaborative approach with the **1st level** has been implemented to leverage existing resources and be seen from outside users as part of the same CCRI umbrella.
- Mapping exercise to identify potential **2nd level** entities.
- Project analyses in WP2 was used as a basis for identifying new potential projects and initiatives to be engaged in the CCRI as **3rd level** entities.
- Open call for expression of interest launched to attract cities and regions to the CCRI Knowledge Hub mentoring programme and became new CCRI pilots (**3rd level**). 9 cities and regions has been selected in the first round of the CCRI mentoring programme.
- Dedicated steps and materials created to engage entities in the **2nd level** and **3rd level**.
- Monitoring tool to follow the process of new or potential partnering organisations (**2nd level**) and new projects, pilots and fellows (**3rd level**).
- A common Gantt of preliminary activities for the **1st level**, **2nd level**, and **3rd level**.

Next steps:

- **1st level** – Continuous communication and collaborative approach with periodic meetings, emails exchange and updating sharing tools.
- **2nd level** – Follow the protocol defined to engage during the project implementation 5 new partner organisations.
- **3rd level** - The non-selected cities in the call for expression of interest will be invited to participate in the workshops organised by the CCRI Knowledge Hub as participants; those participating in the activities proposed would be considered as fellows.
- **3rd level** - A second open call for expression of interest will be launched in June to start with the mentoring programme in September 2025.

The Network Coordination Guidelines is a “living document”, thus, its content may be adapted throughout the project duration to reflect changes within the project network coordination procedures. A new version of the deliverable is foreseen on month 33 (September 26).

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

Circular Cities and Regions Initiative Knowledge Hub (CCRI Knowledge Hub) aims to increase the impact of the existing Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) by enlarging the network of involved stakeholders, bringing together the knowledge and critical mass already developed around Circular Economy (CE) implementation and building upon the CE stakeholder platform. The goal is to promote and make the CE concept a reality in EU cities and regions, particularly those in the early stage of CE transition.

To reach its objective, CCRI Knowledge Hub acts as a “Knowledge Hub”, leveraging existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of CE in EU cities and regions. CCRI Knowledge Hub’s formula is based on **three principles**: (a) easy access to systematised workable knowledge; (b) tailored mentoring according to users’ needs; and (c) effective awareness-raising to make the CE more desirable, that build upon **four main dimensions**: (i) Public engagement; (ii) Innovation and technology; (iii) Business models and financial support; and (iv) Impact evaluation.

CCRI Knowledge Hub gathers a multidisciplinary expert consortium of 11 partners from 6 EU countries (research and technological centres, universities, research organisations, international networks and associations, regional authorities as well as specialised companies and SMEs) that bring in complementary skills and competences to achieve the project’s objectives.

Figure 1 – CCRI Knowledge Hub’s formula

Project basic data:

- Duration: 1st of January 2024 - 31st of December 2026 (36 months).
- Maximum grant (as stated in the annex 2 of the Grant Agreement, GA): 2.612.932,04€.
- Project number: 101135174

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- Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-CircBio-01-1
- Type of action: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)

1.2. Deliverable Purpose & Scope

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide **practical guidelines describing in detail the coordination mechanisms and tools** to be used to ensure effective coordination between CCRI Knowledge Hub, the DG Research and Innovation, the CCRI-Coordination and Support Office (CSO), other CCRI supporters (the sister project CCRI-CSA, the European Investment Bank's – EIB - Circular City Centre; and the Circle Economy), and other partnering organisations and interested stakeholders. This document contains a description of the following aspects:

- 3-level circular model of Collaboration, Coordination and Cooperation
- Coordination and communication tools within the three levels of coordination

The Network Coordination Guidelines is a “living document”, thus, its content may be adapted throughout the project duration to reflect changes within the project network coordination procedures. A preliminary version was agreed by partners and submitted to the Project Officer on month 3 (March 2024) and now a new version is submitted in month 15 (March 2025). An updated version will be submitted in month 33 (September 26).

1.3. Document's Audience

The **main audience of the document** are CCRI Knowledge Hub partners, the DG Research and Innovation and CCRI-CSO, as this deliverable aims to provide crucial information to project participants, guiding them on various aspects of the CCRI Knowledge Hub network and support procedures aligned with the CCRI. Additionally, this document is listed in the Description of Action (DoA) as “public”, i.e. it is intended to be made available to a wider audience, including the European Commission (EC) and appointed independent expert reviewers. By being publicly accessible, it ensures transparency and accountability, allowing stakeholders to gain insights into the project's coordination approach and procedures aligned with the CCRI.

1.4. Related documents

The following documents have been necessary to develop D1.2 Network Coordination Guidelines:

- CCRI Knowledge Hub DoA, which is annex 1 to the GA n° 101135174 and contains the details of how the action (project) is being carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
- CCRI Knowledge Hub D1.1 Project management handbook that describes the different levels of coordination and communication inside and outside the consortium.

1.5. Acronyms

CA: Consortium Agreement	CSA: Coordination and Support Action
CCRI: Circular cities and regions initiative	DoA: Description of Action
CCRI-CSO: Circular cities and regions initiative coordination & support office	EC: European Commission
CCRI-CSA: Circular cities and regions initiative coordination and support action	EIB: European Investment Bank
CE: Circular Economy	GA: Grant Agreement
	KVC: Kveloce (project coordinator)
	RTD: DG Research & Innovation

2. Three levels of coordination

As described in the DoA, to guarantee that the work of CCRI Knowledge Hub complements and enhances the CCRI activities, to avoid repetition and to make the most of the cooperation with other networks/initiatives and available resources, a 3-level “Circular model of Collaboration, Coordination and Cooperation” is planned (figure 2):

- 1st level:** With the CCRI (EC, RTD), the CCRI-CSO, and other CCRI supporters (CCRI-CSA project, EIB and Circle Economy).
- 2nd level:** with the potential new partnering organisations.
- 3rd level:** with the potential new CCRI pilots, fellows, projects, partnering organisations members, and other interested stakeholders.

Figure 2 - Overview of the 3-level circular model of collaboration, coordination and cooperation

Inspired by the CE concept, CCRI Knowledge Hub aims to apply a circular model to its project coordination where CCRI Knowledge Hub, the CCRI (EC, RTD), the CCRI-CSO and other supporters share, re-use, and rethink existing knowledge and activities to make the most of available resources and create further value for the CCRI community. This is the circular model of collaboration, coordination, and cooperation that CCRI Knowledge Hub aims to implement

to support the CCRI to leverage the existing knowledge on CE to make the concept a reality within European cities and regions. In this sense, and for the purpose of this model, we understand as collaboration, coordination, and cooperation the following:

- **Collaboration:** CCRI Knowledge Hub, the CCRI (EC and RTD), the CCRI-CSO and other supporters work together to implement certain common actions (i.e. common campaigns, common capacity building activities) defined and agreed upon previously and in continuous dialogue between the entities.
- **Coordination:** CCRI Knowledge Hub, the CCRI, the CCRI-CSO and other supporters have a common plan of activities and shared responsibilities to avoid duplication of their work and to advance in a common direction. In fact, they are considered part of the same umbrella, and outside users perceive the CCRI and its supporters as one common initiative.
- **Cooperation:** CCRI Knowledge Hub, the CCRI, the CCRI-CSO and other supporters create synergies between each other, their members, and external stakeholders to achieve the same goal, which is to accelerate the implementation of CE in European cities and regions.

It is important to mention that after the first conversations with the CCRI and the CCRI-CSO, the **focus of CCRI Knowledge Hub is to enlarge the CCRI network with new members**. This is the reason to adapt the audiences mentioned in the 2nd and 3rd level to new potential members and not the members already engaged in the CCRI as described in the DoA. Nevertheless, all activities performed by CCRI Knowledge Hub will be open and accessible to all CCRI members as they will be implemented under the umbrella of the CCRI.

In the following sections, a detailed description of each level of collaboration, coordination and cooperation is provided.

3. CCRI Knowledge Hub coordination with level 1: CCRI and CCRI - CSO

The **1st level** of collaboration, coordination and cooperation aims at ensuring and maintaining a continuous, sound, and effective management and communication flow with the CCRI (EC and RTD), the CCRI-CSO, and other CCRI supporters (the CSA sister project of CCRI Knowledge Hub, the EIB and the Circle Economy) to ensure that the objectives are aligned, and the activities are complementary, meaningful, and reinforcing.

In summary, the purpose of this coordination level is, as described in the DoA (figure 3): *ensure goals alignment, shared planning, information exchange, ongoing communication, ensuring complementary of the activities and avoiding duplication, cooperative logistics, identifying potential risks and mitigation measures and ensuring participation in CCRI events*. These goals will be achieved via **close communication, shared tools, and collaborative approach** among CCRI Knowledge Hub, the RTD, the CCRI-CSO and the other CCRI supporters.

Figure 3 - Overview of the 1st level of the circular model of collaboration, coordination and cooperation

For **close communication** purposes, CCRI Knowledge Hub, the RTD and the CCRI-CSO have agreed to maintain fast exchange of emails, periodic meetings, and ad-hoc meetings when needed. In this sense, at the beginning of the project the main contacts from RTD, the CCRI-CSO and KVC had been shared some concrete rules: always keep the EC/ RTD in copy of any exchanges with the CCRI-CSO and add always the email CCRI-CSO@ecorys.com (functional mailbox). Moreover, the following meetings had been proposed in the CCRI Knowledge Hub DoA and, afterwards, agreed with RTD, and the CCRI-CSO:

- **An initial meeting at the beginning of the project (✓):** in fact, before the project kick-off-meeting, two meetings between CCRI Knowledge Hub, RTD, and the CCRI-CSO were held:
 - The 15th of January 2024 (online) with the main aim of sharing CCRI Knowledge Hub approach and methodology with the CCRI-CSO and starting to explore complementarities between both teams.
 - The 25th of January 2024 (in-person, Brussels) to continue working on the common approach and complementarities between CCRI Knowledge Hub and CCRI-CSO.
- **Periodic monthly meetings (online):** they have been scheduled every second Monday of the month from 14.00 to 15.00 (1h duration). All CCRI Knowledge Hub project partners are invited to participate in these meetings. A dedicated agenda is shared at least two days in advance so that partners can add any point to be discussed and the RTD/CCRI-CSO can have an overview of the points to be discussed and, therefore, decide about their participation.
- **Review meetings every 6 months (face-to-face):** if possible, jointly with the CCRI Knowledge Hub transnational project meetings (see table 1):

Table 1 – CCRI Knowledge Hub face-to-face meetings

Event	Partner Responsible	Location
Kick Off Meeting (M1-January 2024) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	KVC	Brussels, BELGIUM
2 nd Project meeting (M6-June 2024) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICONS	Milan, ITALY
3 rd Project meeting (M11 -November 2024) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EURADA	Brussels, BELGIUM
4 th Project meeting (M18-June 2025)	VTT	Espoo, FINLAND
5 th Project meeting (M24 -December 2025 – it will be organised to coincide with the CCRI conference if possible)	ALDA	Strasbourg, FRANCE
6 th Project meeting (M30 - June 2026)	CETEC	Murcia, SPAIN
Final event (M36-December 2026)	KVC	Brussels, BELGIUM

- Meetings on demand: whenever necessary.
For example, at the beginning of the project some thematic meetings were organised between CCRI Knowledge Hub, RTD, and the CCRI-CSO on the following topics:
 - Potential CCRI Knowledge Hub **platform** integration in the existing CCRI website (14th of February 2024). For this meeting, the main contacts exchanged between KVC, RTD, the CCRI-CSO were enlarged with the CCRI Knowledge Hub partner in charge of the platform (Inveniam).
These meetings had been maintained over time involving the required agents to analyse the suitability of an API (Application Programming Interface).
 - Common **visual identity and communication and dissemination actions** (12th of February 2024). In this case, the CCRI Knowledge Hub partner in charge of the communication and dissemination strategy and activities, ICONS, was invited to have a dedicated meeting with the main contacts from KVC, RTD, and the CCRI-CSO. In this meeting, it was agreed to have a dedicated shared folder for CCRI KH partners and the CCRI-CSO to work together on communication, sharing events, responsibilities, calendars, etc.
These continuous exchange of information and meetings between RTD, CCRI-CSO and ICONS are maintained for all the communication actions.

With the new CSA, **monthly coordination meetings** between the RTD, CSO, CSA, EIB and CCRI Knowledge Hub were promoted by the CSO to align efforts under the CCRI umbrella. A **shared tool** in Excel format was agreed among supporters aimed to provide a snapshot of the main CCRI support offers and help to understand the “big picture”. A shared space in teams is also available to share documents, mainly for communication purposes. In addition, **on demand meetings** had been organised to agree on concrete topics such as the case studies/good practices been analysed by different supporters and try to have common titles and layout.

Finally, all the actions designed and implemented from CCRI Knowledge Hub follow a **collaborative approach** with RTD, CSO, and the other CCRI supporters. As example, a common open call for expression of interest for external experts had been launched with the CSO to identify external mentors for the mentoring programme (CCRI Knowledge Hub) and the on-demand advisory assignments (CSO). Another example is related to the communication actions promoted by the CCRI Knowledge Hub, all of them follow the CCRI communication guide and the CCRI media relations toolkit and are agreed with RTD and CSO before their publication.

4. CCRI Knowledge Hub coordination with level 2: partnering organisations

The purpose of the **2nd level** of collaboration, coordination and cooperation is, as described in the DoA (figure 4): *presentation of the activities, information and good practice exchange, identification of synergies, cooperative logistics, joint activities and identification of experts/mentors.*

Figure 4 - Overview of the 2nd level of the circular model of collaboration, coordination and cooperation

As discussed with the RTD and CCRI-CSO, the CCRI Knowledge Hub is focused on (i) enlarging the CCRI initiative with new partnering organisations and (ii) complementing the activities that the existing partnering organisations are doing.

4.1. Enlarging CCRI partnering organisations

As mentioned, one of the main focus of CCRI Knowledge Hub is to engage more partnering organisations in the CCRI. In fact, in the CCRI Knowledge Hub DoA a detailed list of potential new partnering organisations was identified and the links with CCRI Knowledge Hub partners highlighted (table 2).

Table 2 - Organisations actively working on CE to be potential partnering organisations of the CCRI

C40 Cities: Connects cities to take climate action, towards a healthier and more sustainable future.

Multiple projects exploring how city governments can take a lead in the transition to a circular economy. Tools, knowledge sharing and support for cities to plan, measure and implement action. **Membership or contacts: ALDA**

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Circular Economy Club: Raise awareness and bring together local community to develop local CE strategies.

Organisation of global events: The Circular Economy Cities Week. **Membership or contacts: EURADA**

EUROCITIES: Facilitates sharing of knowledge among cities on CE best practises and case studies

Task force on circular economy: best practises, knowledge exchange on how to overcome barriers posed by the linear economy model. Case studies and policy recommendations. **Membership or contacts: EURADA, ICONS**

Italian Cluster of Circular Bioeconomy

Over 120 members, representing all the entities operating in the circular bioeconomy. **Membership or contacts: ICONS**

PREVENT Waste Alliance -> NOT INTERESTED

Platform for knowledge exchange and international cooperation. **Membership or contacts: CETEC**

Moreover, a **mapping exercise** of new potential partnering organisations has been done at the beginning of the project that will be continuously update along the project implementation. In this sense, CCRI Knowledge Hub partners stay alert to any organisation likely to become a partnering organisation and identified or contacted as consequence of the project activities (good practices analysis, capacity building activities, participation in events, etc.). Special attention will be paid to potential partnering organisations coming from the academia and industrial side, as requested by the RTD and CSO. Following also their advance, the CCRI Knowledge Hub is focused on potential partnering organisations from outside the CCRI and will only engage in this process entities inside the CCRI network that directly express their willingness to became part of the CCRI as partnering organisation.

The **steps** followed by CCRI Knowledge Hub to engage new partnering organisations are the following (figure 5):

Figure 5 - Steps to engage new partnering organisations

1. Contact via email the organisations susceptible to be partnering organisations by the CCRI Knowledge Hub partner who has the contact or, if there is no previous contact, by the project coordinator (KVC). The content of this email entails: a brief description of the CCRI, targeted messages based on the analysis of why the potential partnering

organisations could be interested in joining the CCRI, the benefits of being part of the network and an invitation to have an online meeting to go in-depth to the opportunities of being a member. An example of this email is included as Annex 8.1.

2. If the entity express interest to be CCRI partner organisation, KVC organises a bilateral online meeting where the CCRI is presented in depth together with the benefits to be partnering organisation, participation possibilities (such as the CCRI Thematic Working Groups), obligations, and the process to become a partnering organisation.
3. After the meeting, the entity (if still interested) should complete a questionnaire facilitated by the CCRI-CSO and propose some concrete actions for collaboration with the CCRI. KVC supports the entity filling the questionnaire and giving ideas for the actions to be proposed. All this information is then shared with RTD and CCRI-CSO.
4. If needed, a dedicated meeting with the RTD and the CCRI-CSO is organised to deepen the benefits and process and to solve doubts.
5. Support in the process to become a CCRI partnering organisation. CCRI Knowledge Hub will support the entity in the process if they agree to be part of the CCRI network.

Throughout the process, CCRI Knowledge Hub members are available to solve doubts via email or to organise extra online meetings to solve doubts or clarify any aspects needed by the partnering organisation candidates.

Following this process, the CCRI Knowledge Hub is supporting RECONOMY in the process to be partnering organisation and contacting previous entities (table 2 and those derived from the mapping exercise) to explore their interest to be partnering organisations. For instance, Prevent Waste Alliance forwarded us to GIZ (a German office for international cooperation), a service provider in the field of international cooperation for sustainable development and international education. After some conversations with them, we understand that the figure of partnering organisation is not suitable for them, but they would like to be inform about CCRI knowledge Hub activities, so they had been included the next level of coordination.

An internal **monitoring tool** (excel file) has been established to follow the process of new partnering organisations engagement and continuously report the status to the RTD and CCRI-CSO.

4.2. Complement the activities being implemented by the CCRI partnering organisations

At the beginning of the CCRI Knowledge Hub lifecycle, partners analysed the activities being implemented by the CCRI partnering organisations to not overlap with the planned activities within the CCRI Knowledge Hub DoA. In this sense, CCRI Knowledge Hub aims to complement the actions being implemented to address new topics, topics that need more attention, complementary services, and engage new partnering organisations. For example, and according to the first conversation with RTD and CCRI-CSO, from the four main domains addressed in the CCRI Knowledge Hub, **more efforts will be dedicated to technology and impact evaluation**, as the other two cross-cutting topics are already covered by the OECD (public engagement) and the EIB (funding). The activities implemented by CCRI Knowledge Hub will be available to existing CCRI members or to newcomers.

4.3. Periodic meetings

Once the new organisation has been engaged following the process described in figure 5 and the cooperation agreements are settled, an introductory meeting will be organised between the new partnering organisation, CCRI Knowledge Hub, RTD and CCRI-CSO. Then, every 4 months online or in-person meetings will be held between CCRI Knowledge Hub and the new partnering organisation (also the RTD and CCRI-CSO will be invited) to support the entity in their new role of CCRI partnering organisation. In this sense, RECONOMY was invited to participate in the in-person workshop implemented in month 9 (September 2024 in Valencia, Spain) where two representatives participated. They, together with new potential partnering organisations will be invited to next online and in-person workshops to be held in month 23/24 (November/December 2025 in Brussels, Belgium) and month 32 (August 2026 in Milan, Italy). These in-person meetings will be combined with in-person meetings with the 3rd level of coordination (pilots, fellows, projects and partnering organisation members) and capacity building activities. In addition, close communication via email and phone calls will be established to support them in the firsts months of being partnering organisations.

5. CCRI Knowledge Hub coordination with level 3: pilots, projects and fellows

The 3rd level of collaboration, coordination and cooperation aims at: (i) enlarging the CCRI network with new projects, pilots and fellows, and (ii) complement the already ongoing activities implemented by the CCRI to ensure and maintain a profiting relationship with the CCRI projects, pilots, fellows and partnering organisation members and other interested stakeholders.

In summary, the purpose of this coordination level is, as described in the DoA (figure 6) is: *to present the activities, to collect the feedback and suggestions, to gather information and to evaluate the members’ satisfaction about the support provided with the information collected.* In addition, as agreed with RTD, the CCRI and CCRI-CSO, the focus of CCRI KH will be to complement the support already provided by the CCRI-CSO to pilots, fellows and projects with the planned services and to enlarge the existing network.

Figure 6 - Overview of the 3rd level of the circular model of collaboration, coordination and cooperation

5.1. Enlarging the CCRI pilots, fellows and projects

The analysis of projects and initiatives performed in WP2 will be the basis for identifying new potential projects and initiatives to be engaged in the CCRI. In addition, the capacity building activities and the mentorship support services will also be a keyway to engage new cities and regions in the CCRI (new pilots and fellows). Also, the participation of CCRI Knowledge Hub partners in different events will be a good opportunity to engage newcomers to the CCRI. For that, a common calendar has been created in the working space of CCRI Knowledge Hub where partners identify interesting events, who is attending and what the purpose to attend that event is. Moreover, EURADA (the European Association of Development Agencies) and the other networks involved in the consortium (EBN – European Business and Innovation Centre Network - and ALDA – European Association for Local Democracy) play a key role in disseminating knowledge among its members, acting as multipliers enlarging the user base, fostering stakeholders' engagement and inviting newcomers to join the CE community.

Special focus will be made to engage new members coming from academia and business, as requested by the CCRI. Although the activities implemented to enlarge the network will consider the quintuple helix (business, civil society, academia, public administration, and environmental organisations).

The process to engage **new pilots and fellows** follows a different approach (figure 7):

Figure 7 - Steps to engage new projects

1. An open call for expression of interest has been launched to attract cities and regions in the CCRI Knowledge Hub mentoring programme and enlarge the CCRI network. The text of the call is included as annex 8.2. For that reason, the expression of interest stated that “The CCRI Knowledge Hub welcomes a diverse range of cities and regions, encouraging participation from all locations and backgrounds to foster a vibrant, inclusive community. Cities and regions already receiving support from the CCRI-CSO as Pilots are not eligible to participate in this CCRI Mentoring Programme. The objective is to enlarge the CCRI community and welcome newcomers”.
2. After the deadline, a total of 9 cities and regions were selected to receive the mentoring programme and, therefore, be **pilots** of the CCRI receiving this support (Figure 8). The non-selected cities will be invited to participate in the workshops organised by the CCRI Knowledge Hub as participants, and some of them in a more advance stage to CE can

be invited as speakers. In this sense, those participating in the activities proposed would be considered as **fellows**.

Figure 8 – CCRI knowledge Hub pilot cities (first round)

A second open call for expression of interest will be launched in June to start with the mentoring programme in September 2025. This second round will be focused to attract cities and regions from underrepresented countries in the CCRI and will follow the same process. Non-selected cities and regions in the first round will be susceptible to be part in the second round of the mentoring programme.

The process to engage **new projects** in the CCRI will follow the same steps described in the previous section for the new partnering organisations (figure 9) with some adaptations:

Figure 9 - Steps to engage new projects

1. Contact via email. The CCRI Knowledge Hub will contact via email those projects selected as good practice in the WP2 to inform them about the CCRI and their potential collaboration in the initiative (working groups, events, etc.). This contact will be made once the good practices analysis is made (expected by March 2025) with the main aim

also to engage them in the CCRI Knowledge Hub online workshops planned from March to May 2025. Further contents will be planned aligned with future online and in-person workshops. Other interesting projects coming from the CCRI Knowledge Hubs activities will be contacted in the same way. Activities such as: participation in events to promote the CCRI Knowledge Hub and the CCRI as part of the WP4, identification of CE resources as part of the WP2 activities and exploring new cities/regions and potential experts for the WP3 activities.

2. A dedicated meeting will be organised if needed to present the CCRI to the project coordinator and the collaboration opportunities.
3. If the project is not already published in the CCRI website as consequence of the activities developed in the WP2, a dedicated template will be shared with them to be completed to appear on the CCRI website with the requested fields. The information will be shared with the CCRI-CSO and RTD to be uploaded. CCRI Knowledge Hub will support in all this process.

Also, an internal **monitoring tool** has been established to follow the process of new projects, fellows and pilots' engagement and continuously report the status to the RTD and CCRI-CSO.

5.2. Complementing the existing services provided by the CCRI-CSO

As described along this document, CCRI Knowledge Hub aims to complement the existing services provided by the CCRI to pilots, fellows, and projects. In this sense, the **mentoring programme** is being provided to cities and regions that are not pilots in the CCRI website (to enlarge the existing network). Moreover, our mentoring programme is addressed to cities and regions in their early stages of their process to implement CE systematic solutions and mainly offers support around for domains: (i) Public engagement; (ii) Innovation and technology; (iii) Business models and financial support; and (iv) Impact evaluation. In relation to the **capacity building activities**, and following the DoA, CCRI Knowledge Hub will share the initial planning with the RTD and CCRI-CSO to explore synergies, complementarities, and joint activities.

5.3. Periodic meetings

As agreed with the RTD and the CCRI-CSO, all communication with existing CCRI members (projects, pilots and fellows) should be undertaken by the CCRI-CSO, as they have already been in contact with these members. The reason behind this is not to confuse already engaged members with new contact details and new people but rather to act as one joint team. Having this in mind, the planned "introductory meetings" described in the DoA with CCRI pilots, fellows' project coordinators and partnering organisations had been changed for promotional materials that presented the CCRI Knowledge Hub and its services (CCRI website, newsletters and social media). In the same sense, the "annual meetings" with CCRI pilots, fellows, project coordinators and partnering organisations had been changed for more aligned activities with this umbrella approach. The "introductory and annual meetings" with new members are maintained as a mean to engage newcomers in the network and accompany them in their first steps inside the CCRI. For instance, introductory meetings with the 9 cities and regions selected as pilots has been performed by CCRI Knowledge Hub partners. In these meetings,

the CCRI was presented with all the existing services and tools before starting with the exchange of information needed to design the support pathway (prior to the mentoring programme).

As described in the 2nd level of collaboration, coordination and cooperation, new pilots, fellows, projects and members of the partnering organisations were invited to participate in the in-person meetings planned in month 9 (September 2024 in Valencia, Spain) and will be invited to participate in the following in-person meetings planned in month 23/24 (November/December 2025 in Brussels, Belgium) and month 32 (August 2026 in Milan, Italy). These in-person meetings will be combined with in-person meetings with the 2nd level of coordination (partnering organisations) and capacity building activities. In addition, close communication with them via email and phone calls will be established to support them in the firsts months of participating in the CCRI.

6. Three levels of coordination – common Gantt

The following Gantt (figure 10) provides an overview of the meetings planned for the 3 levels of coordination, collaboration and cooperation. Nevertheless, they are flexible to be adapted to the CCRI requests and the demands of the CCRI new partnering organisations, fellows, pilots, projects and members of the partnering organisations.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23 (24)	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
	jan-24	feb-24	march-24	ap-24	may-24	jun-24	Jul-24	ag-24	sept-24	oct-24	nov-24	dic-24	jan-25	feb-25	march-25	ap-25	may-25	Jun-25	Jul-25	ag-25	sep-25	oct-25	nov/dic 25	jan-26	feb-26	marc-26	apr-26	may-26	Jun-26	Jul-26	ag-26	sep-26	oct-26	nov-26	dic-26	
Project in-person meetings	KVC					ICONS						EURADA						VIT						ALDA												KVC
Location	BE					IT		ES				BE						FI						BE						ES						BE
3Cs: 1st level																																				
Monthly meetings (KVC responsible)			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
In-person meetings (KVC responsible)	X					X						X						X					X						X							X
3Cs: 2nd level																																				
4 months meetings (KVC responsible)														X				X					X							X						X
In-person meetings								UVEG																EBN										ICONS		
3Cs: 3rd level																																				
annual meetings (KVC responsible)														X															X							X
In-person meetings								UVEG																EBN										ICONS		

Figure 10 - 3 levels of coordination, communication and collaboration common Gantt

For the **in-person meetings** with the different levels of coordination, a dedicated partner has been appointed to host the meeting with a dedicated budget. For the 1st level meetings, KVC, as project coordinator, was the responsible to draft the agenda and lead the sessions, but for the 2nd and 3rd level, the responsible to organise the content and lead the sessions will be the partner responsible to host the meeting, with the support of KVC and the rest of the CCRI Knowledge Hub project partners who will also attend the in-person meetings. The preliminary agenda will be sent by the responsible partner one month in advance once approved by the CCRI Knowledge Hub partners. After the meeting, the minutes will be shared with the attendants also by the responsible partner once approved by the CCRI Knowledge Hub partners.

For the **online meetings**, KVC, as project coordinator, created the regular meetings via Microsoft Teams and send the agenda in advance and the related minutes after the meeting. Also, approval of the CCRI Knowledge Hub partners is requested before sending the agenda and corresponding minutes.

7. Conclusions

The D1.2 presents the practical and agreed guidelines to ensure an effective coordination between the CCRI knowledge Hub inside the CCRI umbrella led by RTD and supported by the CCRI-CSO and other supporters, willing to enlarge the CCRI network with new partnering organisations and interested stakeholders based on a 3-level circular model of Collaboration, Coordination and Cooperation:

1st level: With the CCRI (EC, RTD), the CCRI-CSO, and other CCRI supporters (CCRI-CSA project, EIB and Circle Economy).

2nd level: with the potential new partnering organisations.

3rd level: with the potential new CCRI pilots, fellows, projects, partnering organisations members, and other interested stakeholders.

The purpose of the coordination **1st level** is, as described in the DoA: to ensure goals alignment, shared planning, information exchange, ongoing communication, ensure complementary of the activities and avoid duplication, cooperative logistics, identifying potential risks and mitigation measures and ensure participation in CCRI events. For the close communication purposes, CCRI Knowledge Hub, RTD, and CCRI-CSO has agreed in maintaining fast exchange of emails, periodic meetings, and ad hoc meetings when needed. In this sense, at the beginning of the project the main contacts from RTD, CCRI-CSO and KVC had been shared with some concrete rules: always keep the EC and RTD in copy of any exchanges with the CCRI-CSO (CCRI-CSO@ecorys.com (functional mailbox)). Moreover, the following meetings had been agreed:

- An initial meeting at the beginning of the project (✅): Already done.
- Periodic monthly meetings (online): they had been fixed every second Monday of the month from 14.00 to 15.00 (1h duration).
- Review meetings every 6 months (face-to-face): if possible, jointly to the CCRI KH transnational project meetings.
- Meetings on demand: whenever necessary.

In addition, regular meetings and shared tools has been established with other supporters (CSA, EIB and Circle Economy) to align the work under the CCRI umbrella.

The **2nd level** aims at (i) enlarging the CCRI initiative with new partnering organisations and (ii) complementing the activities that the existing partnering organisations are doing, with new topics, topics that need more attention, complementary services, etc (i.e. more efforts dedicated to technology and impact evaluation domains). For that, CCRI Knowledge Hub is mapping new potential partnering organisations, contacting them and supporting them in the process of being partnering organisations with a 5-step process: (i) contact, (ii) dedicated meeting, (iii) questionnaire and proposal of collaborative actions, (iv) meeting with RTD and CCRI-CSO if needed, and (v) support in the process. Once engaged, an introductory meeting will be organised between the new partnering organisation, CCRI Knowledge Hub, RTD and

CCRI-CSO. Then, every 4 months online or in-person meetings will be held between CCRI Knowledge Hub and the new partnering organisation (also RTD and CCRI-CSO will be invited) to support the entity in their new role of CCRI partnering organisation.

The **3rd level** of coordination aims to complement the support already provided by the CCRI-CSO to pilot, fellows and projects with the planned services and enlarge the existing network with new pilots, projects, and fellows. Special focus will be made to engage new members coming from the academia and business, as requested by the CCRI. Although the activities implemented to enlarge the network will consider the quintuple helix (business, civil society, education, public administrations, and environmental organisations). New pilots and fellows are being engaged through an open call for expression of interest. As a result, 9 cities/regions had been selected to be pilots and receiving the mentoring programme offered by the CCRI Knowledge Hub. Non-selected cities and regions will be invited to participate in CCRI Knowledge Hub activities in order to become fellows. The process to engage new projects follow a 3-step process: (i) contact; (ii) meeting; and (iii) support them to provide the requested information, if needed. In both cases (new pilots and fellows), CCRI Knowledge Hub members will be available to solve doubts via email or to organise extra online meetings if needed.

To engage new interested stakeholders in the **2nd level** and **3rd level** a **mapping exercise** has been performed and will be updated during the whole project duration with any organisation likely to become part of the CCRI initiative. An internal **monitoring tool** has been established to follow the process of new members engagement and continuously report the status to RTD and CCRI-CSO.

A **common GANTT** of preliminary agreed activities for the **1st level**, **2nd level**, and **3rd level** is presented in the section 6 of this deliverable and will be shared once the meetings approach in the common repository, to work closely with the RTD and CCRI-CSO.

The **2nd level** and **3rd level** has been invited to participate in the in-person meeting hold in month 9 (September 2024 in Valencia, Spain) and will be invited to participate in the next in-person meetings planned for month 23/24 (November/December 2025 in Brussels, Belgium) and month 32 (August 2026 in Milan, Italy). These in-person meetings will be combined with capacity building activities.

The Network Coordination Guidelines is a “living document”, thus, its content may be adapted throughout the project duration to reflect changes within the project network coordination procedures. In fact, a new version of the deliverable is expected to be submitted in month 33 (September 26).

8. Annexes

Annex 8.1. Email to engage new partnering organisations

Dear Montse,

As part of your regional work on CE, we would like to share with you this information that can be very interesting for your regions and the cities inside your region.

The Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) provides essential **support for European cities and regions transitioning to a circular economy**.

The CCRI Knowledge Hub has **opened a call for cities and regions** that would like to receive tailored support and mentorship in their transition towards circularity. Through the **CCRI Knowledge Hub support pathways**, applicants can receive a diagnostic assessment of their current readiness for the circular economy transition. Based on this assessment, support pathways will be co-designed, and validated with stakeholders from each city or region, ensuring that the assistance provided is highly tailored and relevant to their specific contexts.

Further information is available in the document attached.

Interested participants should express their interest in receiving the CCRI Knowledge Hub support pathways through the [Expression of Interest Online Form](#) by **15 December 2024**.

Kind regards,

**CCRI Knowledge Hub
Coordination team**

CCRIknowledgehub@kveloce.com

Link to website: <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/>

Link to Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135174>

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Annex 8.2. Open call for cities and regions in the CCRI Knowledge Hub mentoring programme

Join the CCRI Mentoring Programme

Call for expression of interest

Background

Launched and funded by the EU as part of the Circular Economy Action Plan, the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) focuses on implementing the circular economy across Europe's cities and regions. One of the key objectives is to support the implementation of circular systemic solutions, addressing different sectors and value chains, involving various actors, and tackling a variety of circularity issues (e.g. business models, regulatory impacts), as well as exerting influence in multiple fields (social, economic, and environmental).

About the CCRI Knowledge Hub

In January 2024 the CCRI Knowledge Hub was launched to support the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative. As its name suggests, it mostly acts as a knowledge hub, consolidating and expanding the knowledge base already available to the CCRI community and providing additional advisory support. The CCRI Knowledge Hub offers a wide range of instruments, including **easily accessible resources**, a **customised mentoring program**, and **effective awareness-raising** initiatives to help cities and regions transition to more sustainable and circular practices. It targets any European cities and regions – including those only starting their circularity transition.

Call for cities and regions

The CCRI is currently growing and as such, working towards deepening the support made available to its community. In this context, the CCRI Knowledge Hub is now launching its **Mentoring Programme** for cities and regions willing to advance their circular transition. As part of this new programme, selected cities and regions will benefit from tailored resources and expert guidance to help them navigate the complexities of transitioning to a circular economy.

The programme will start with a comprehensive diagnostic assessment of their current circular transition readiness. This assessment will be conducted using **CCRI Knowledge Hub's** own methodology, in line with the [CCRI methodology](#) as well as including some

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elements of the CCRI Self-Assessment Tool (developed by the CCRI Coordination and Support Office) where applicable. This preliminary assessment is therefore key for identifying specific needs, challenges, and opportunities unique to each city or region. Based on this assessment, the appointed "mentor" of the CCRI team will co-design – together with stakeholders from each city or region – highly-tailored support pathways so that the assistance provided well meets beneficiaries' needs and takes into consideration the specificities of their local context.

Beneficiary cities and regions will have the opportunity to seek expert mentoring and support across four key thematic areas: (i) **public engagement**, (ii) **innovation and technology**, (iii) **business models and financial support**, and (iv) **impact evaluation**.

In addition, they will be invited to a variety of **workshops, seminars, and events on circular economy**.

Who can participate in the CCRI Mentoring Programme?

The **CCRI Knowledge Hub** welcomes a diverse range of cities and regions, encouraging participation from all locations and backgrounds to foster a vibrant, inclusive community. Cities and regions already receiving support from the CCRI Coordination and Support Office as [Pilots](#) are not eligible to participate in this CCRI Mentoring Programme. The objective is to enlarge the CCRI community and welcome newcomers.

Why participate in the CCRI Knowledge Hub support pathways?

Becoming part of the CCRI mentoring programme offers a unique opportunity to enhance your understanding of the circular economy and gain the support necessary for a successful transition. You should consider applying if:

- € You seek to deepen your knowledge and accelerate the implementation of circular economy practices and strategies.
- € You are committed to advancing circularity but require further guidance on planning and implementing this transition.
- € You are in the early stages of your circular economy journey and need structured support.
- € You are more specifically looking for expert assistance across the four key dimensions of the CCRI Knowledge Hub: public engagement, innovation and technology, business models and financial support, and impact evaluation.

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How to express your interest?

To express your interest in receiving tailored support and mentorship, please send us your **Expression of Interest** through this [online form](#). We will need the contact information of your organisation, and a Letter of Interest signed.

The CCRI Knowledge Hub team will reach out to inform you about the outcome of your application.

Deadline for submission: 15th of December 2024

Contacts:

Project coordinator:

Mirela Ferri, Project Manager at Kveloce mferri@kveloce.com

Communication Manager:

Federica Fusco, Fondazione ICONS federica.fusco@icons.it

CCRI website: www.circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu

CCRI LinkedIn page: www.linkedin.com/company/circular-cities-and-regions-initiative/

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